

OA BOOK USAGE DATA TRUST: IDS TECHNICAL GAP ANALYSIS

ASSESSING TECHNICAL READINESS FOR AN
INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACE

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The scope of this work was to assess operational scholarly publishing service providers for their technical readiness against the IDS core services, to inform the next set of technical work towards achieving an International Data Space.

The five IDS core services are:

- Clearing House
 - App Store Provider
 - Metadata Broker
 - Identity Provider
 - Vocabulary Provider
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METHODOLOGY

TIMELINE

SCORING CRITERIA

We identified the following pillars to consider. Each pillar is considered for each organisation (or service), leading to a final **IDS Readiness Score**, calculated as a weighted average of each section. Scores range from High to Low.

- IDS information security compatibility (20%)
- Existing experience and alignment with IDS (20%)
- Infrastructure (15%)
- Global presence and operations (10%)
- Data management (10%)
- Software development capabilities and sustainability (15%)
- Standards (10%)

RESULTS

KEY RESULTS

- **Information security is typically lacking among organisations specialising in open data/publishing**
 - Given the criticality of infosec to achieve certification within IDS, this is a major gap found across the industry that would need addressing.
- **All organisations scored low on alignment to IDS**
 - Unsurprising because the specification for all five of the IDS services is highly specific.
 - All organizations would need to undertake fairly significant development to create a service aligned with the IDS RAM.
- **The most easily aligned role was the Metadata Broker**
 - Many industry services have been developed to index content and associate metadata specifically to enable the dissemination, discoverability and access to OA books.
- **We were unable to find any services which could fulfil the roles of Clearing House or App Store Provider**
- **There is a lack of understanding and awareness of data spaces and IDS**
 - Not surprising as the IDS is a relatively new concept and has largely been developing within other industries (e.g. manufacturing, supply chains, energy etc).

RESULTS: IDS READINESS SCORES

Metadata Brokers

	IA Scholar/ Internet Archive	Metadata Plus/ Crossref	Registry of OpenAIREGraph/ OpenAIRE	DataCite Commons/ DataCite	Thoth	OA Switchboard	OAEBU Workflows/ COKI	DOAB/ OAPEN
IDSR SCORE	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium-low	Medium-low	Medium-low

Vocabulary Providers

	ROR	Submit, Retrieve, Reuse/ISSN
IDSR SCORE	Medium-low	Medium-low

Identity Providers

	EZProxy/ OCLC	Identity and Access/ Liblynx	TheIPRegistry.org/ PSI
IDSR SCORE	Medium	Medium-low	Low

Score definitions:

High: High technical readiness and closest to IDS operational certification, able to start building and hosting an IDS service with no additional R&D

Medium-high: Minor gaps present, judged to require less effort to close (effort as a combination of time, resources and expertise)

Medium: Few major gaps or many minor gaps that require effort to close

Medium-low: Major gaps in several areas requiring substantial effort to close

Low: Lowest readiness level and far from IDS operational certification, requiring an overwhelming effort to be ready or represents a fundamental organisational incompatibility

RECOMMENDATIONS

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. A single, well-administered IDS to support scholarly outputs is preferred to many.
2. Choose a partner or series of partners with knowledge of IDS architectures and the domain of scholarly communications (such as 67 Bricks) to support in the data model development and technical roadmapping, and in designing, building and operating of the OAeBUDT-IDS.
3. There is an education and inspiration piece of work to be done with organisations in scholarly communications to help them to see the value in an OAeBUDT-IDS.

17 bricks

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